

Momentum/Spatial Bound Quantum States and Particle-Wave Duality?

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Quantum mechanics is often compared with classical mechanics, but it seems that the momentum/spatial treatment of bound quantum mechanics provides for a particle-wave duality with both features having an experimental basis. In bound state quantum mechanics, one has a density pattern often similar to a two slit pattern i.e. with humps, yet at the same time one may knock a particle out of the bound state and obtain a probability distribution $a(p)a(p)$ of momentum states. Describing a particle simply by its momentum even in the bound state seems to be classical as does using $pp/2m$ to describe the kinetic energy of a plane wave in the decomposition of $W(x)$, the wavefunction. Wave aspects are linked to classical particle features like momentum and do not change the particle energy $pp/2m$. The wave, we argue, may be related to some type of periodic cyclic forward backward motion which creates a spatial probability needed to establish resolution on the order of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. It is often not seen unless there is a potential or other probability waves which may interfere with it

In this note, we consider the scenario that momentum (i.e. mov in the nonrelativistic case) is directly linked to a kind of forward-backward cyclic motion of a quantum particle regardless of its spin. The fact that spin exists suggests some kind of internal motion. In the case of a photon, it may be directly linked to angular motion of energy, although for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ matters are more complicated. This motion again does not change classical energy $pp/2m$ unless spin interacts with a magnetic field etc. We argue that a bound state is stochastic and so various free particle momentum states exist without being restricted to an x position. This is the particle scenario. The internal cycling motion, however, gives rise to a resolution of the order of $1/p$ suggesting a spatial distribution to account for such a resolution. Furthermore, the internal cycling (i.e. forward and backwards motion) even for a particle traveling to the right requires two dimensions to describe overall forwards and backwards motion. The spatial density of the cycling motion may be associated with internal changes in velocity, but overall there is a particle with mass m_0 moving with v (nonrelativistic case) and kinetic energy $pp/2m$. This holds for a free particle, but also for a particle in an infinite potential well with a single average $|p|$. An issue occurs, however, if one wishes to form an average of different p values at the same point x . In such a case the spatial probability density $\exp(i p_j x)$ differs for each p at x and so the average $[p_1 \exp(i p_1 x_0) + p_2 \exp(i p_2 x_0)] / [\exp(i p_1 x_0) + \exp(i p_2 x_0)]$ becomes relevant. In other words, one takes the average momentum, say p_1 , and links it to the spatial probability i.e. multiplies two averages and then divides by spatial probability to find a momentum flow at a specific point within a wavelength region. For the particle aspect, such a resolution is non-issue. The particle is the same at each x point in space.

Free Particle

One may wonder why a particle-wave duality for a quantum particle is needed. A nonrelativistic particle has a classical momentum mov which manifests itself in experiments. For example, one may take an ensemble of quantum ground states for a particular $V(x)$ and “knock” out the single particle. In such a way, one obtains a momentum distribution with probabilities

$a(p)a(p)$. There is no knowledge of x and one has in a sense a classical set with average kinetic energy throughout the bound system of:

$$KE_{\text{overall}} = \sum p^2/2m a(p)a(p) \quad ((1))$$

In other words, one assumes Newtonian dynamics applies to quantum particles even though they receive stochastic hits from a potential $V(x)$. Stochastic hits also occur in classical physics and a change from p_1 to p_2 results in a change in kinetic energy from $p_1^2/2m$ to $p_2^2/2m$.

The energy of the bound system E , however, depends on potential energy as well and knowing a momentum distribution does not yield a spatial density immediately which is needed for:

$$PE_{\text{overall}} = \int dx V(x) \text{density}(x) \quad ((2)) \text{ where } KE_{\text{overall}} = \int dx KE(x) \text{density}(x)$$

$$\text{such that: } PE_{\text{overall}} + KE_{\text{overall}} = E \text{ and } \int dx \text{density}(x) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

Thus, the pure particle scenario must be somehow linked to a spatial density. The big question is how to obtain such a spatial density.

We argue that quantum objects, regardless of spin, may have a kind of internal cycling (back and forward motion) linked to a spatial resolution or wavelength of the order of $1/p$. If there is resolution of space on the order of a certain length, one expects a probability distribution in this length because this creates the resolution. Constant probability means no resolution. Yet, this resolution is based on $p=mv$ which is a constant and assumes constant probability at each point i.e. the particle picture. As a crude analogy, consider a rolling wheel with a mass m on a thin wire wheel. To first order, the classical momentum is mv , yet there is internal rotation directly linked to p . In some cases, this internal cycling related to resolution has no direct effect on momentum i.e. energy flow. It does, however, affect overall energy i.e. there is now a rotational and translational part whereas for quantum particles there is only a translational part. One may also note that a circularly polarized photon has energy pc , but an angular momentum of 1.

A free particle moves through space with momentum p and kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ at each x like a classical particle. Even for the quantum case of a particle in an infinite well, p and $p^2/2m$ are constant for each x though the spatial probability is $A \sin(px)$ (origin at $x=0$). If one considers p multiplied by the spatial probability at a specific x as representing flow, then it is divided by the same spatial probability leaving momentum at each x .

To find a specific probability distribution, we suggest using:

$$\begin{aligned} |\cos(px) - \sin(px)| |a(px)| &= \exp(dx \, d/dx) |a(px)| \quad ((2b)) \\ |\sin(px) + \cos(px)| |b(px)| & \quad |b(px)| \end{aligned}$$

A solution is $a(px) = \cos(px)$ and $b(px) = \sin(px)$. One may note that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may be both positive and negative suggesting forward/backward periodic motion, thus to have overall

forward and backward motion, one needs two dimensions. Another point is that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ have opposite parity. This may lead to different bound states with different parities. For example, an oscillator has various energy solutions with shifting parities. Due to the particle/wave duality, the solution $\exp(ipx)$ should be able to reproduce a classical particle even within a wavelength distance. We argue that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ yields this property and suggests that the overall spatial probability $W(x)$ needs to undergo $W^*(x)W(x)$ before it becomes a spatial density. In this note, we call $W(x)$, the wavefunction, spatial probability.

A problem only arises if there are different p_j 's at the same x . In such a case, one may write:

$$[p_j \text{ spatial probability } (p_j x) + p_i \text{ spatial probability } (p_i x)] / [\text{spatial probability } (p_j x) + \text{spatial probability } (p_i x)] \quad ((3))$$

In other words, one creates an average momentum flow divided by an average spatial probability at x . This gives rise to non-classical effects. One may ask how spatial probability for a single particle may change within a wavelength. Just as in classical physics where one defines a spatial density by $dt = dx/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ =velocity), one may use a similar analogy in the quantum case. If a particle is present $dt/ dt \ll 1$ in a region dx_1 then it only seems that the particle is hardly present in the interval dt and this will be conveyed by experimental data even though the particle was clearly there. For example, if the x axis is separated into equally spaced dx units then a high speed particle traverses dx in a much shorter time than a slow one, but one may be using a fixed dt interval to measure the density especially if one averages over particles of different speeds. In such a case, it seems that the fast particle was hardly there relative to a fixed dt . Time becomes linked to the concept of density. (We will examine later how this classical density is linked to quantum density for high energy levels i.e. the correspondence principle.)

Thus, it only seems that a particle is hardly present at x and so its momentum p or kinetic energy $pp/2m$ reflect this by being multiplied by spatial probability. One may wonder why this is necessary, but it may be important for reactions with a potential which may resolve distances on the order of the wavelength. Even though the spatial probability does not change p or $pp/2m$, the reaction time at position x may be so small that it seems that the particle is hardly present. This seems to give rise to interactions affected by $\cos(px)$.

As noted, this becomes important if one adds various p_j contributions in a bound state. How does one interpret negative values of spatial probability from $\cos(px)$? One may argue that there is a direction in space defined by the x axis direction. Consider a box dx with only the left hand border as one moves to the right. If the cycling motion is to the right, it is in the same direction as the x axis motion, but if it is to the left, it is as if the particle probability is leaving the cell. In such a case one loses p and $pp/2m$. This leads to the effect of interference even of kinetic energies.

In the quantum case, one uses the spatial probability $\exp(ipx)$ to determine the apparent presence of a particle at x within a wavelength. What about the idea of dt ? A fast moving particle has a much shorter dx i.e. wavelength than a slow moving one? This means that for a fixed dt , a high p will generate more short wavelength cycles than a low p . Within each cycle, however, each particle is treated the same. Thus, at a given x , one wishes to know where each "p" is within its cycle. The value for all p values is within 0 and i.e. the limits of \cos or \sin .

For different p values, one has not only $\exp(ipx)$, but $a(p)$ weights determined by the potential. This ensures that the average kinetic energy, computed using the strange spatial probability approach at x plus $V(x)$ equals E at all x points. One cannot use the particle approach to calculate $KE(x)$ because a particle with momentum p knocked out of the bound system does not carry information about its location. It may have come from any x point, yet the free particle kinetic energy $pp/2m$ is used together with a spatial probability to refine what a measuring device or potential sees within the wavelength length.

Correspondence Principle

The correspondence principle states that classical spatial density $dt = dx/v(x)$ where $v(x) =$ classical velocity should match quantum bound density for high energy levels. Quantum density is often a series of humps such that $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x) = E - V(x)$. $KE(x)$ matches the classical kinetic energy at x exactly, but the spatial density is very different. It was noted that for different p 's in the quantum bound state, one has different wavelength values proportional to $1/p$. For a classical system, the distance from one hump center to another may be taken as equal to dx for high energy. Following classical physics, $v(x)$, i.e. $v_{rms}(x)$ from quantum mechanics, should be roughly constant within dx . In such a case, $dx = v_{rms}(x) dt$ or $dt = dx / v_{rms}(x)$. Thus, the area under a curve drawn from one hump center to the next (and touching other humps) should represent dt , the time the particle spent within that region.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum particle, regardless of spin, undergoes a kind of cyclic motion related to spatial resolution i.e. a wavelength of the order $1/p$ which does not change its classical momentum p or energy $pp/2m$. Thus, there is a kind of duality. On the one hand, "wave" type motion is present, but is a little difficult to detect, but on the other, basic features of a classical particle are present. We argue that this cyclic motion is linked to equating a rotation matrix in $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ (acting on a two vector) to a translation operator. Thus, the particle has a fixed momentum mov (nonrelativistic) which is classical and particle-like and this drives the cycling back and forth motion which creates a spatial probability $\exp(ipx)$ within the wavelength region to establish spatial resolution. This resolution or spatial density becomes important when trying to establish the overall spatial probability when averaging over more than one p . For a given x , each p_j is at a different point in its cycle i.e. has different $\exp(ip_j x)$ value which is multiplied by the quantity being average e.g. p_j or $p_j^2/2m$ etc. The sum is divided by the sum of the spatial probability. This leads to interference effects. Negative spatial probability (i.e. negative $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ values mean that the particle within the wavelength region appears to leave a dx cell (i.e. it moves backwards then forwards etc). Weights for the various $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $a(p)$ are chosen such that average kinetic energy at each x is classical i.e. $E - V(x)$. The fact that one creates averages using classical values p_j or $p_j^2/2m$ seems to imply that the classical particle picture is also in effect. Experimentally this is the case as one may knock out particles from an ensemble of single particle bound states to find the $a(p)a(p)$ values. On the

other hand, the cycling-resolution feature (the wave feature) manifests itself in both bound states and two slit interference etc.

In classical physics, a combined situation of momentum p to the right as well as some kind of rotational motion as in a rolling wheel leads to mechanical differences (i.e. a different energy) than a particle with only momentum p . In quantum mechanics, there does not seem to be this difference (although one does not physically have a rolling wheel picture), there seems to be some kind of periodic back and forth motion with an extra dimension (just as in the wheel picture) required to describe forward and backward motion (rolling).